

Ghost pearlite as a transient state in a high-strength Fe-Mn-C steel

Marcel Muench^{*a}, Jan Lars Riedel^b, Sandipan Sen^b, Si Gao^c, Wu Gong^d, Yolita M. Eggeler^e, Nobuhiro Tsuji^c, Martin Heilmaier^b and Alexander Kauffmann^a

^a Institute for Materials (IM), Ruhr University Bochum (RUB), Universitätsstraße 150, 44780 Bochum, Germany

^b Institute for Applied Materials (IAM-WK), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Kaiserstraße 12, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

^c Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Kyoto University, Sakyo-kyu, Kyoto 606-8501, Japan

^d J-PARC Center, Japan Atomic Energy Agency, Tokai-mura, Naka-gun, Ibaraki 319-1195, Japan

^e Laboratory for Electron Microscopy (LEM), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Engesserstraße 7, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

* corresponding author

mail: marcel.muench-l4k@rub.de (M. Muench)

phone: +49 234 32 18158

Abstract

1 Short time austenitization (STA) of Mn-partitioned pearlite provides access to chemically patterned
2 austenitic-martensitic ($\gamma + \alpha'$) microstructures in Fe-Mn-C steels, frequently referred to as ghost pearlite.
3 In the present work, a near-eutectoid Fe-4.9Mn-2.7C (at.%) alloy was used to investigate the relationship
4 between Mn homogenization, phase evolution, retained austenite (γ) stability, and mechanical behavior.
5 Starting from pearlite with pronounced Mn enrichment in cementite (θ), STA treatments of 150 s, 400 s,
6 and 5000 s were applied prior to quenching. After a complete transformation to γ , an immediate
7 transition from ghost pearlite to microstructures consisting of increasingly homogeneous domains of
8 mixed lath/block martensite (α') with retained γ commences. Thermodynamic and kinetic calculations
9 indicate that the STA step can be described by transformation to γ without Mn repartitioning, followed
10 by Mn homogenization within γ . On this basis, both the microstructure evolution and the retained γ
11 fractions after quenching can be predicted from a small set of physically meaningful input parameters.
12 All conditions exhibit very high compressive strength, with 5 % off-set yield strengths (σ_{p5}) beyond
13 2500 MPa, and substantial deformation-induced martensitic transformation. The 400 s treatment
14 possesses the highest work hardening capability, demonstrating that partial Mn homogenization is more
15 beneficial than either complete morphological inheritance or complete homogenization. Thus,
16 controlled Mn homogenization emerges as a promising design strategy for chemically patterned Fe-Mn-
17 C steels.

Keywords

18 Pearlite, Ghost Pearlite, Chemical Patterning, Fe-Mn-C, AHSS

1. Introduction

19 Advanced high-strength steels (AHSS) derive their mechanical performance from carefully adjusted
20 microstructures that combine high strength while maintaining good ductility [1–3]. This combination is
21 achieved by activating several strengthening and work hardening mechanisms within complex
22 multiphase microstructures, often organized across different length scales. Depending on alloy concepts
23 and processing routes, these microstructures may include ferrite, bainite, martensite, retained austenite,
24 carbides and various defect structures. Their mechanical response is not governed by any single
25 constituent, but by the interaction between phases, interfaces, local chemistry and deformation
26 mechanisms. A central objective in AHSS design is therefore to maintain a high work hardening capacity
27 over a sufficiently wide deformation range, so that plastic instability and damage are delayed [1–3]. In
28 Mn-containing steels, this can be achieved by exploiting metastable austenite (γ). Its response during
29 deformation depends on thermodynamic stability, stacking fault energy (SFE), size, morphology,
30 chemical composition and the mechanical constraint imposed by the surrounding phases. Mn is therefore
31 a key alloying element, because it stabilizes γ and modifies the SFE, thereby enabling deformation-
32 induced martensitic transformation (DIMT) and, under suitable conditions, deformation twinning [4, 5].
33 The benefit of retained γ is, however, restricted to a suitable stability window. If γ is too unstable, it
34 transforms at the onset of plastic deformation, and the transformation-induced hardening contribution is
35 rapidly exhausted. If γ is too stable, transformation is obstructed and the potential contribution of DIMT
36 remains unused before failure. The most favorable response is therefore expected when γ transforms
37 progressively during deformation, distributing the transformation-induced hardening contribution over
38 an extended strain interval. The central challenge is thus not only to generate metastable γ , but to control
39 its distribution and stability in a targeted manner to facilitate uniform deformation with continuous high
40 work hardening.

41 Several established AHSS processing concepts address this challenge by stabilizing retained γ through
42 solute partitioning. Quenching and partitioning [6, 7] treatments mainly rely on C partitioning from
43 martensite (α') to γ at comparatively low temperatures, whereas intercritical annealing [8–10] enables
44 the enrichment of γ in both C and Mn. In both cases, the final γ fraction, chemistry and stability are
45 closely linked to the annealing response and to the initial microstructure. A promising, alternative
46 processing strategy was introduced by Sun et al. [11] and is based on the creation of a lateral Mn
47 concentration pattern during pearlite formation, followed by short time austenitization (STA) and
48 quenching. In this approach, Mn-enriched and Mn-depleted regions are first established on the scale of
49 the pearlitic microstructure. If subsequent austenitization is sufficiently short, this chemical pattern is
50 not fully removed during and after the transformation to γ . Quenching then converts the Mn-lean regions
51 to α' , while Mn-rich regions remain as metastable γ . In this way, chemically patterned $\gamma + \alpha'$
52 microstructures can be synthesized in which not only phase fractions, but also length scale and local
53 phase stability, can be adjusted through the preceding pearlite. Due to the relatively high C content
54 required for pearlite formation and high α' fraction, the resulting $\gamma + \alpha'$ microstructures exhibit ultra-
55 high strength potential beyond 2000 MPa [11]. Avoiding premature failure and actually reaching such
56 high strength remains challenging when designing AHSS [1]. An earlier study by Wang et al. [12] on a
57 microstructure that comprises α' and γ nanolaminates showed that the distinct morphology not only
58 promotes strength, but also high work hardening and damage tolerance. Thus, the concept developed by

59 Sun et al. [11] has attracted interest as it enables the design of unique chemically patterned $\gamma + \alpha'$
60 microstructures that combine morphological refinement with promising mechanical properties [13–21].

61 This processing route was considered to be restricted by local equilibrium (LE) arguments, according to
62 which Mn partitioning during pearlite formation should be thermodynamically required at the interfaces
63 between γ and both ferrite (α) as well as cementite (θ) [22–24]. Recently, we showed that this is not
64 necessary [25]. Substantial global Mn partitioning into θ can already be achieved when partitioning is
65 thermodynamically required only at the α/γ interface, without a substantial reduction in the degree of
66 partitioning. The subsequent microstructure evolution during STA, in contrast, is still insufficiently
67 understood. First exploratory studies of this processing route were carried out for hypoeutectoid alloys
68 containing less than 3.8 at.% Mn, revealing a gradual increase of domains without inherited morphology,
69 while ghost pearlite domains diminish with increasing dwell time [13, 21]. Ideally, understanding the
70 mechanisms that govern STA processing would enable the design of phase fractions and γ stability.
71 Whether such control can in fact be achieved, how the corresponding transient microstructures develop,
72 and how they affect the final mechanical response nevertheless remains unresolved.

73 Therefore, the present study examines the microstructural evolution and mechanical behavior of a near-
74 eutectoid Fe-4.9Mn-2.7C (all compositions in at.%, unless stated otherwise) alloy starting from Mn-
75 partitioned pearlite. STA treatments of 150 s, 400 s, and 5000 s were applied prior to quenching to
76 systematically vary the inherited Mn profile and, thus, the degree of chemical inhomogeneity. Attention
77 is given to ghost pearlite as a transient state and to the relevant intermediate microstructures achieved
78 after longer dwell times. Previous mechanical assessments of such microstructures relied on tempering
79 to suppress premature tensile failure and to enable meaningful plastic deformation [13, 21]. In contrast,
80 the present work focuses on the as-quenched condition in to reveal the intrinsic effects of Mn patterning,
81 morphology evolution and retained γ stability. Microstructure analysis was carried out by combining
82 electron microscopy, atom probe tomography, neutron diffraction and DICTRA simulations, to assess
83 the interplay between Mn homogenization, phase evolution and retained γ stability. Quasi-static
84 mechanical properties were examined by hardness and compression testing. The latter was selected
85 because it allows (i) efficient screening of relevant parameters with a limited volume of material, (ii)
86 investigating intrinsic work hardening without the interference of otherwise ductility-limiting factors
87 and (iii) easy batchwise STA processing, due to the relatively small sample size.

2. Materials, Experiments and Simulations

88 The alloy was produced by arc melting high-purity elements together with an in-house synthesized Fe_3C
89 precursor. The synthesis was followed by a homogenization treatment at 1100 °C for 96 h under flowing
90 Ar. The chemical composition was determined after homogenization by optical emission spectroscopy
91 (OES) with a Mn content of (4.9 ± 0.3) at% and C content of (2.7 ± 0.1) at%. Pearlite transformation
92 was carried out by austenitization in a box furnace at 910 °C for 1 h, an immediate transfer to a furnace
93 set to 575 °C with isothermal holding for 24 h and subsequent oil quenching.

94 For further processing and analysis cylindrical compression testing samples with 3 mm in diameter and
95 5 mm in height were sectioned from the pearlite-treated alloy via wire electronic discharge machining
96 (EDM). Subsequent STA treatments were performed batchwise with five samples per hold time at
97 $T_{\text{STA}} = 770$ °C for 100, 150, 400, and 5000 s. The STA was concluded by oil quenching. To increase
98 the heating rate, the specimens were covered in preheated Al_2O_3 powder. These conditions are referred
99 to as STA100, STA150, STA400, and STA5000, respectively. STA100 is not discussed in the main
100 manuscript, because the microstructure showed incomplete transformation to γ . A corresponding

101 micrograph is provided in Figure S2 of the Supplementary Material. Further details about alloy
102 processing and heat treatments are given in our previous publication [25].

103 Metallographic preparation was carried out by water-cooled grinding with SiC paper followed by
104 polishing with 3 μm as well as 1 μm diamond suspensions and finalized via an OPS polishing step using
105 MasterMet-2 (Buehler, USA). Samples were then etched in a 1 % Nital solution for 5 s.

106 Microstructure characterization was carried out using a Leo Gemini 1530 field-emission scanning
107 electron microscope (SEM) by Zeiss (Germany), utilizing backscattered electron (BSE) contrast
108 imaging. The analysis contains the quantification of volume fractions of fibrous, lamellar and chemically
109 homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ domains, apparent lamellar spacing and true lamellar spacing. Quantification of
110 domain specific volume fractions was done manually with ten micrographs and a total area of
111 $\sim 22,000 \mu\text{m}^2$ by using the ImageJ software [26]. The morphologies present in the investigated
112 conditions are lamellar, fibrous and lath- or plate-like. Lath and plate morphologies correspond to
113 chemically homogenous regions of coarse α' and retained γ . Besides domain-specific volume fractions,
114 the ratios of fibrous to lamellar morphology were calculated, which allows preferential dissolution to be
115 investigated. The ratios were calculated separately for each micrograph and then averaged. The reported
116 uncertainty corresponds to the standard error of the mean. Fibers oriented parallel to the sample surface
117 were identified as lamellae, as they are indistinguishable in such orientation.

118 The determination of interface spacing was restricted to lamellar regions, as the fibers are
119 inhomogeneous in terms of size and spacing even in the same colony. The apparent lamellar spacing
120 s_{app} at the sample surface was measured for all conditions exhibiting such regions. In total ten colonies
121 were considered per condition. True lamellar spacing s_1 can be determined from s_{app} and the inclination
122 angle φ_1 of the lamellae towards the surface following $s_1 = \sin(\varphi_1) \cdot s_{\text{app}}$. φ_1 were determined from
123 cross sections. Corresponding trenches were done orthogonally to the lamellar orientation via focused
124 ion beam (FIB) milling with a Helios G4 dual beam FIB/SEM by Thermo Fisher Scientific (USA). In
125 total five colonies were analyzed. This analysis was limited to pearlite, as ghost pearlite shows
126 insufficient contrast in cross-sectional imaging. An example of such a micrograph is shown in Figure S3
127 of the Supplementary Material. Using low current ion beam imaging for enhanced phase- and orientation
128 contrast, a complex nano-scale microstructure with varying orientation within the α' lamellae is
129 revealed. This effectively obstructs a similar determination of φ_1 for the ghost pearlite. Therefore, a
130 conversion factor was calculated based on the data of pearlite, which allows for the comparison of true
131 lamellar spacing between all conditions.

132 Local phase compositions were assessed by considering both energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
133 (EDS) by scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and 3D atom probe tomography (APT).
134 Due to the limited accuracy of carbon quantification by STEM-EDS, APT was selected because of its
135 higher compositional accuracy and spatial resolution for the present analysis [27]. Experiments were
136 performed on all conditions using a LEAP 4000X HR (Cameca, France) in laser mode. APT tips were
137 prepared by FIB milling with an Auriga 60 dual beam FIB/SEM (Zeiss, Germany). To increase stability
138 during evaporation, some tips were coated with Cr, following Ref. [28]. The composition of the
139 constituting phases was determined in a robust way with volumes containing at least one million ions.
140 Additionally, peak decomposition was carried out using AP Suite 6.3 (Cameca, France). The procedure
141 uses unique peaks of the same species and charge state, together with natural isotopic abundances, to
142 separate overlapping contributions. 1D concentration profiles were taken at three random positions
143 across a region of interest. To improve visibility, the standard deviations of the individual measurements
144 are omitted.

145 Phase identification for pearlite and thus validation of a complete transformation was done by means of
 146 transmission synchrotron XRD. Considering the beam size and the sample thickness of approximately
 147 300 μm , a statistically relevant volume of $\sim 120000 \mu\text{m}^3$ was probed. The experiment was done at
 148 beamline BL13XU, SPring-8 of the Japan Synchrotron Radiation Research Institute (JASRI), using
 149 monochromatic synchrotron radiation at an energy of 30 keV ($\lambda = 0.0413 \text{ nm}$) and 30 s exposure time.
 150 The calibration of the $2\theta_d$ zero-shift and sample displacement was done with a standard specimen of
 151 ceria (CeO_2).

152 Neutron diffraction experiments to determine lattice constants and phase fractions of the STA conditions
 153 were carried out at beam line (BL) 19 TAKUMI of the Materials and Life Science Experimental Facility
 154 (MLF) at Japan Proton Accelerator Research Complex (J-PARC) [29]. All experiments were conducted
 155 ex-situ on the STA conditions, each before and after compression testing. Structural refinements for the
 156 determination of lattice parameters and phase fractions were done with the software GSAS-II [30] by
 157 fitting individual peaks with a pseudo-Voigt type function. The martensite present in the STA conditions
 158 was fitted with a body-centered tetragonal prototype (BCT, space group $I 4/m m m$) denoted as α' . To
 159 minimize the effect by preferred colony orientation, six peaks were analyzed for γ and ten for α' . Lattice
 160 parameters a_γ were calculated for γ by

$$\frac{1}{d_{\gamma,hkl}^2} = \frac{h^2 + k^2 + l^2}{a_\gamma^2} \quad 1$$

161 and $a_{\alpha'}$ and $c_{\alpha'}$ for α' by

$$\frac{1}{d_{\alpha',hkl}^2} = \frac{h^2 + k^2}{a_{\alpha'}^2} + \frac{l^2}{c_{\alpha'}^2} \quad 2$$

162 d_{hkl} is the spacing of a $\{hkl\}$ plane. The volume fraction f_γ was calculated by

$$f_\gamma = \frac{\frac{V_\gamma}{n_\gamma} \sum_{x=0}^{n_\gamma} S_\gamma^x}{\frac{V_\gamma}{n_\gamma} \sum_{x=0}^{n_\gamma} S_\gamma^x + \frac{V_{\alpha'}}{n_{\alpha'}} \sum_{x=0}^{n_{\alpha'}} S_{\alpha'}^x} \quad 3$$

163 with V_i as the cell volume, S_i^x as peak-specific scale factor and n_i as the number of analyzed peaks of
 164 phase i .

165 Vickers hardness testing was carried out on metallographically prepared specimens using a Qness
 166 Q10A+ hardness tester (ATM Qness GmbH, Germany). The hardness, H , was calculated from the
 167 average diagonal length of the indentation d_H according to $H = 0.189 \cdot F \cdot d_H^{-2}$. For each condition,
 168 ten indents were applied under a load of 9.8 N. The mean hardness and corresponding standard deviation
 169 were determined.

170 Room-temperature (RT) compression tests were carried out using a Z100 electromechanical universal
 171 testing machine (Zwick GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Compression testing was chosen to enable
 172 efficient screening of relevant parameters from a limited volume of material, since a comparatively large
 173 number of specimens can be prepared and tested. In addition, this approach allows the deformation
 174 behavior to be investigated in the as-quenched condition without premature brittle failure. The
 175 experiments were performed under displacement-controlled conditions with an initial strain rate of $\dot{\epsilon} =$

176 10^{-3} s^{-1} . Testing was deliberately stopped after reaching a total compressive strain of (10–13) %. Four
177 samples were tested per condition.

178 To simulate Mn homogenization during STA, DICTRA simulations were carried out using Thermo-
179 Calc software (USA) with the thermodynamic database TCFE10 and the kinetic database MOBFE5.
180 Details on the simulations are provided in Chapter 3.2.

3. Microstructure Evolution

3.1. Experimental Results

181 Figure 1 shows representative micrographs of the initial pearlite, STA150, STA400 and STA5000
182 conditions in a), b), c) and d), respectively. These conditions were chosen, because they represent
183 distinct microstructural stages during STA processing. To develop an understanding of the
184 microstructure evolution during STA, key parameters of the different conditions in an undeformed state
185 were determined and compared to the initial pearlite.

186 The pearlite is entirely comprised of $\alpha + \theta$, which aligns with our previous findings on alloys also
187 processed in the same α/γ partitioning regime [25]. The corresponding diffraction pattern is shown in
188 Figure S1 of the Supplementary Material. Despite pearlite being described as a lamellar reaction product
189 of alternating α and θ when referring to the binary system [31, 32], Fe-Mn-C pearlite exhibits lamellar
190 and fibrous θ morphologies [25]. The different morphologies are indicated in Figure 1 a) in red for
191 lamellar and yellow for fibrous regions. The volume fraction of fibrous regions, f_f , was determined to
192 be (0.29 ± 0.16) .

193 The STA conditions are exclusively comprised of $\gamma + \alpha'$. The corresponding neutron diffraction pattern
194 of STA150 is shown in Figure S5. Using laboratory-based diffraction techniques, no reports on
195 hexagonal ϵ martensite exist for the present microstructures [11, 13, 21]. However, the applied methods
196 may not be sufficient to exclude small ϵ fractions with certainty. Within the resolution of the neutron
197 diffraction data, no ϵ martensite was detected. This is illustrated in the example of a single peak
198 refinement of an STA150 sample depicted in Figure 7 a). STA150 and STA400 are both partially
199 comprised of ghost pearlite, a $\gamma + \alpha'$ microstructure, which inherits its morphology from the initial
200 pearlite. Despite pearlite and ghost pearlite sharing the same morphology, they can be easily
201 distinguished due to a contrast inversion after etching (see Figure 1 a) and b)). Besides ghost pearlite,
202 STA150 and STA400 show domains of chemically homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$, with both lath and plate α'
203 morphologies [33, 34]. The latter will be called homogenous $\gamma + \alpha'$ throughout the manuscript. Those
204 domains amount to a volume fraction f_{hom} of (0.10 ± 0.06) for STA150 and to (0.82 ± 0.05) for
205 STA400, while STA5000 is entirely comprised of them. The corresponding data is summarized in
206 Table 1.

Figure 1: SEM-BSE micrographs (Nital etching): a) initial pearlite, b) STA150, c) STA400, and d) STA5000. Lamellar morphology is marked by red, fibrous by yellow arrows. Blue arrows indicate homogeneous domains without retained morphology exhibiting a mixed lath and plate $\gamma + \alpha'$ microstructure.

207 The morphology ratio f_f/f_l was determined for pearlite, STA150 and STA400 with (0.52 ± 0.16) ,
 208 (0.82 ± 0.27) and (1.32 ± 0.25) , respectively. While the fraction of chemically homogeneous regions
 209 continuously increases, the proportion of fibrous target microstructure is increasing, indicating a higher
 210 stability of fibers against homogenization.

211 Furthermore, the lamellar spacings of the same conditions were measured. Due to limitations in
 212 determining the tilt angle, the true lamellar spacing s_l was only determined for pearlite with
 213 (180 ± 18) nm. The average s_l is smaller than the apparent lamellar spacing s_{app} of (197 ± 56) nm by a
 214 factor of (0.92 ± 0.28) . This factor remains valid for the STA conditions, as no change in average
 215 inclination of the corresponding domains is expected. Comparing the s_l of pearlite with the calculated
 216 s_l of STA150 and STA400 a continuous increase can be observed from (180 ± 18) nm to (187 ± 65) nm
 217 to (235 ± 102) nm. This increase suggests that, upon increasing dwell time, domains of higher interface
 218 spacing remain more stable against the homogenization of Mn.

219

220

221

222

223

224

225

226

Table 1: Morphology evolution over STA duration with f_f , f_l , and f_{hom} as global volume fractions of fibrous, lamellar and homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ regions, respectively. The morphology ratio f_f/f_l was calculated separately for each pair of values and then averaged. The reported uncertainty corresponds to the standard error of the mean. * marks calculated s_l data based on the conversion factor (0.92 ± 0.28) and s_{app} .

	Morphology volume fraction			Morphology ratio	Apparent lamellar spacing	True lamellar spacing
	f_f	f_l	f_{hom}	f_f/f_l	s_{app} nm	s_l nm
Pearlite	0.29 ± 0.16	0.71 ± 0.16	–	0.52 ± 0.16	197 ± 56	180 ± 18
STA150	0.34 ± 0.25	0.56 ± 0.26	0.10 ± 0.06	0.82 ± 0.27	204 ± 34	$187 \pm 65^*$
STA400	0.09 ± 0.03	0.09 ± 0.05	0.82 ± 0.05	1.32 ± 0.25	256 ± 81	$235 \pm 102^*$
STA5000	–	–	1	–	–	–

227 The local chemical composition of all STA conditions was investigated via APT. A quantitative
228 summary of the investigations is given in Table 2. Data listed for STA150 and STA400 correspond to
229 ghost pearlite domains. The Mn and C concentrations, expressed as x_{Mn} and x_C respectively, were
230 determined for the relevant phases from selected volumes within the reconstructed APT datasets, with
231 interfacial regions excluded from the analysis. Multiple tips were tested for each condition, which were
232 used to determine error ranges. In case of STA150 no error range is given for the γ phase, as only a
233 single tip comprising γ was tested successfully. However, the result was validated by several
234 measurements of α' . Representative ion distribution maps as well as 2D Mn concentration maps are
235 shown in Figure 2 a) to d) for pearlite, STA150, STA400 and STA5000, respectively. The corresponding
236 1D concentration profiles are depicted in Figure 3 a) to d). Datasets a), b), c) presented in Figure 2 and
237 Figure 3 were collected from lamellar regions. Comparing the Mn content within θ , and for the STA
238 conditions within γ , a clear reduction was obtained from (25.7 ± 3.0) at.% to 10.4 at.% for STA150 and
239 to (7.6 ± 0.1) at.% for STA400. In case of STA5000, the Mn distribution was found to be entirely
240 homogeneous in the volumes investigated. The overlapping data points in Figure 3 a) might appear as
241 if a Mn enrichment at the α/θ interface is present. However, this is an artifact attributed to the limited
242 volumes considered for the 1D profiles. Taking the 2D Mn distribution presented in Figure 2 a) into
243 account, no such local enrichment is observed. Furthermore, no γ/α' interface segregation of C or Mn
244 was found in ghost pearlite, which can be seen in Figure 3 b) and c). Accompanying the reduction in
245 Mn peak concentration is a general broadening of the Mn concentration profile. Considering the peak
246 width at a fixed Mn content of 4 at.%, an increase from (9 ± 0) nm to (73 ± 4) nm to (80 ± 2) nm occurs.
247 It must be noted that the initial Mn profiles of STA150 and STA400 are unknown. While the C
248 distributions in the ghost pearlite of STA150 and STA400 appear homogeneous between γ and α' in
249 Figure 3 b) and c), respectively, the phase specific quantification reveals a slight C enrichment within γ
250 compared to α' with 3.1 at.% vs. (2.0 ± 0.2) at.% for STA150 and (2.9 ± 0.1) at.% vs. (2.1 ± 0.2) at.%
251 for STA400.

Figure 2: APT of all conditions with reconstructed ion distribution and 2D Mn concentration map for: a) the initial pearlite, b) STA150, c) a lamellar region of STA400 and d) STA5000. e) depicts the reconstructed C ion distribution, as well as 2D C and Mn concentration maps. A magnified region is depicted within the light red box together with a 1D concentration profile of C along the black arrow.

252 Besides pearlite and ghost pearlite, homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ regions were also investigated. While STA5000
 253 is entirely comprised of such regions, STA400 shows a f_{hom} of (0.82 ± 0.05) . As no difference in terms
 254 of local composition and element distribution was found between the two, the domain will be discussed
 255 for STA400 as an example. In Figure 2 e) the C ion distribution, as well as 2D concentration maps for
 256 C and Mn of a reconstructed tip are shown. The tip exhibits an interface, which is decorated with small
 257 regions enriched in C. These zones are further visualized in the magnified 2D concentration map and a
 258 1D concentration profile, the position of which is indicated via a black arrow. These local C enrichments
 259 are also found in the remaining volume of the tip in a lenticular shape with a thickness of < 10 nm. In
 260 steels containing plate martensite such local C enrichment can be traced back to both dislocations and
 261 interfaces. This is observed even in the quenched condition [35]. The Mn distribution remains
 262 homogeneous throughout the tip. Comparable C distribution with segregation at potential defects was
 263 found in all otherwise chemically homogeneous α' domains, irrespective of the morphology.

Figure 3: 1D concentration profiles of Mn as red data points and C as turquoise data points for: a) initial pearlite, b) STA150, c) STA400, and d) STA5000.

264 Phase fractions and corresponding lattice constants of all STA conditions were determined from neutron
 265 diffraction data and are summarized in Table 4. Despite changes in microstructure with respect to
 266 interface spacing and morphology, all conditions show a comparable f_γ of (0.27 ± 0.03) for STA150 as
 267 well as STA400, and (0.24 ± 0.03) for STA5000. The γ lattice parameter a_γ was determined to be
 268 (3.593 ± 0.004) Å for all STA conditions. The lattice parameter of γ may also be calculated using the
 269 empirical formula [36]:

$$a_\gamma = 3.556 \text{ \AA} + (453.0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ \AA wt. \%}^{-1})w_C + (9.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ \AA wt. \%}^{-1})w_{Mn} \quad 4$$

270 with w_C and w_{Mn} as the C and Mn content in wt.%. Assuming the γ composition of STA150 as the
 271 highest and the overall alloy composition as the lowest possible input, the calculation yields a range of
 272 $(3.588\text{--}3.597)$ Å, which aligns well with the experimental data. For α' the lattice parameters will be
 273 discussed in terms of $c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$ ratio to investigate a potential change in tetragonal distortion. Again, all
 274 conditions show nearly equal ratios in the range of (1.023 ± 0.002) . Lu et al. [37] determined the $c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$
 275 evolution of binary Fe-C alloys with increasing C content via high resolution XRD. They found a linear
 276 dependency following:

$$\frac{c_{\alpha'}}{a_{\alpha'}} = 1 + (45 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ wt. \%}^{-1}) w_C \quad 5$$

277 Calculating again with the lowest and highest possible experimentally determined C content, yields
 278 $(1.020\text{--}1.027)$, which agrees well with the STA data. However, this calculation does not consider any
 279 contribution by dissolved Mn.

Table 2: Global chemical analysis of the alloy via OES as well as local analysis of all microstructures done via APT. For STA400, domains with lamellar morphology are listed. Due to the limited volume that is considered in APT, the composition is given as an average including the range from lowest to highest amount measured. * marks count corrected data, to account for the error in C determination in θ .

	Tips	Phase	Composition	
			x_{Mn}	x_{C}
at.%				
OES	–	–	4.9 ± 0.3	2.7 ± 0.1
Pearlite	6	θ	$25.7 \pm 3.0^*$	25.0^*
	10	α	2.2 ± 0.3	$7 \cdot 10^{-5} \pm 6 \cdot 10^{-5}$
STA150	1	γ	10.4	3.1
	3	α'	3.4 ± 0.4	2.0 ± 0.1
STA400	2	γ	7.6 ± 0.1	2.9 ± 0.1
	3	α'	2.9 ± 0.2	2.1 ± 0.2
STA5000	–	γ	–	–
	2	α'	5.1 ± 0.2	2.4 ± 0.2

3.2. Discussion

280 A near eutectoid Fe-4.9Mn-2.7C alloy was subjected to a pearlite treatment fulfilling the Mn partitioning
281 criterion only for α/γ , but not for θ/γ and therefore outside the partitioning regimes, which were
282 previously established in literature [22–24]. Still, a complete transformation with significant Mn
283 enrichment in θ of (23.6–28.8) at.% was achieved, consistent with earlier assessments on the partitioning
284 behavior of ternary Fe-Mn-C pearlite [25]. Upon performing the STA, the alloy undergoes two distinct
285 microstructural transitions with increasing dwell time. (i) The first is the transformation from pearlite to
286 chemically patterned γ , including intermediate states in which both domains coexist. An example of this
287 condition after quenching is shown in Figure S2 after a hold time of ~ 100 s. (ii) The second is the local
288 homogenization of such chemically patterned γ , leading to a homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ microstructure after
289 quenching. Mixed intermediate states are observed before complete homogenization. Although such a
290 development was observed in Refs. [13, 21], the underlying mechanisms remain incompletely
291 understood.

292 Following complete re-austenitization in stage (i), Mn homogenization can be described as a diffusion
293 problem in single-phase γ . By representing the lamellar and fibrous morphologies as plate-like and
294 cylindrical geometries, respectively, the problem can be reduced to periodic 1D diffusion in planar and
295 radial coordinates [38]. To perform quantitatively meaningful simulations of stage (ii), the initial
296 condition is required to capture both the relevant experimental length scales and the local chemical
297 composition. The characteristic length scales can be obtained directly from the microstructural
298 measurements summarized in Table 1. The local chemical composition depends on the transformation
299 during stage (i), especially on whether Mn repartitions at the moving γ /pearlite reaction front.

300 With respect to (i), several studies investigated the dissolution of partitioned pearlite in Fe-Cr-C and Fe-
301 Mn-C alloys [39–43]. These works proposed a partition to non-partition transition temperature, at which

302 the reaction changes from slow kinetics at low temperatures, accompanied by local homogenization, to
303 fast kinetics with the chemical pattern being retained at high temperatures [39–43]. This temperature
304 was termed partition to no-partition transition temperature (PNTT) by Xia et al. [42]. PNTT is based on
305 LE considerations at the moving γ/α and γ/θ interfaces and its calculation requires the compositions of
306 α and θ . Using the approach for lamellar pearlite by Li et al. [39] and the APT data presented in Table 2,
307 PNTT was calculated to be ~ 741 °C for the present alloy. As $T_{STA} > PNTT$, the transformation can be
308 expected to occur fast and with negligible Mn homogenization.

309 On this basis, DICTRA simulations were performed to study (ii) the dissolution of the chemical Mn
310 pattern after complete transformation to γ . The initial state of the simulation assumes an instantaneous
311 transformation from pearlite to γ without Mn diffusion. The Mn profile is therefore represented as sharp
312 and stepwise, whereas C is assumed to be homogeneously distributed. The average C and Mn
313 compositions of each simulation cell were fixed to $\bar{x}_C = 2.7$ at. % and $\bar{x}_{Mn} = 4.9$ at. %, to match the
314 overall alloy composition. The adjustable parameters of the simulation are (a) the simulation cell size,
315 (b) the position of the Mn step, and (c) the initial Mn compositions. (a) and (b) were chosen such that
316 the simulation cell represents half of the lamellar/fiber spacing, $s_{l/f}/2$, starting from the lamella/fiber
317 center at $d = 0$ nm. In this way, (a) defines the lamellar/fiber spacing $s_{l/f}$ of the initial pearlite, (b) the
318 pearlite's θ volume fraction f_θ , and (c) the Mn content of the former α and θ with x_{Mn}^α and x_{Mn}^θ ,
319 respectively. The simulation times were chosen to represent STA150 and STA400. They were set 100 s
320 shorter than the nominal experimental holding times to account for the experimentally confirmed time
321 of ~ 100 s required to complete the γ transformation. All simulations were performed isothermally at
322 770 °C to match T_{STA} . Within this framework, the simulations are first used to describe the effect of
323 specific pearlite inhomogeneities on the subsequent microstructure evolution. Subsequently, average
324 experimental data of a lamellar pearlite colony will be used to calculate retained f_γ with increasing STA
325 dwell time. For this calculation, the coupled redistribution of C must also be considered. Although C is
326 initially set to a homogeneous concentration, Mn lowers the activity of C in γ , a_C^γ , at a given C content.
327 Consequently, local Mn enrichment introduces gradients in a_C^γ , which promote C redistribution towards
328 Mn-rich regions. This coupling has only a minor influence on the comparison of Mn homogenization
329 rates, but it is essential for predicting local γ stability and retained γ fractions.

330 Figure 4 a) shows the effect of varying *lamellar* spacing, $s_{l1} = 200$ nm and $s_{l2} = 100$ nm, while
331 keeping all other parameters constant, i.e. $x_{Mn}^\theta = 26.0$ at. %, $x_{Mn}^\alpha = 2.0$ at. % and $f_\theta = 0.12$ of the
332 former pearlite. After a simulated dwell time of 50 s and 300 s (corresponding to STA150 and STA400
333 in the experiments), colonies with $s_{l2} < s_{l1}$ homogenize expectedly faster than colonies with s_{l1} . The
334 differences in peak Mn content after different dwell times are indicated via vertical black arrows in
335 Figure 4 a). After 300 s, the peak Mn contents for s_{l1} and s_{l2} are ~ 9 at. % and ~ 5 at. %, respectively.
336 The simulated Mn profiles in γ can now be compared to APT data presented in Figure 3, to deduce their
337 behavior upon quenching. The peak Mn content of retained γ lamellae in the STA400 condition shown
338 in Figure 3 c) is ~ 8 at. %. This suggests that colonies with s_{l1} can retain γ in lamellar morphology after
339 quenching, as 9 at. % $>$ 8 at. %. The simulated Mn profile with s_{l2} is already close to homogeneity
340 after 300 s. A comparable Mn distribution was found for the homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ domains of the STA
341 400 and STA5000 conditions, as depicted in Figure 2 e) and Figure 3 d), respectively. This indicates
342 that a peak Mn content of ~ 5 at. % is insufficient to retain γ in lamellar morphology. Thus, if the
343 microstructure comprises *lamellar* colonies of different lamellar spacing, e.g. s_{l1} and s_{l2} , quenching
344 after 300 s leads to a mixed microstructure of ghost pearlite and homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ domains. A further

345 argument for this behavior is the increase in experimental s_1 with increasing STA dwell time, suggesting
 346 that regions with large spacing retain their morphology longer than more refined ones.

347 An additional, but often neglected, source of inhomogeneity in Mn-partitioned Fe-Mn-C pearlite is the
 348 occurrence of *lamellar* and *fibrous* θ morphologies. To assess their influence on microstructure
 349 evolution, both geometries were simulated using the same initial parameters, including lamellar/fiber
 350 spacing of $s_{11} = s_{f1} = 200$ nm. The fiber cross section was assumed as circular. The only free variable
 351 is then the radius of the θ fiber, r_f . To determine r_f , an equilateral triangle with a side length equal to
 352 the fiber spacing s_f is considered, with one θ fiber located on each corner. The total area of this triangle
 353 is made up of θ and α according to their fractions f_θ and $1 - f_\theta$, respectively. The area of the triangle,
 354 A_t , and that of a single θ fiber, A_f , are then correlated via $A_f/2 = f_\theta A_t$. Solving for the fiber radius
 355 yields $r_f = 36$ nm, which is considerably larger than the lamella-half thickness of only 12 nm. This is
 356 consistent with experimental observations of θ fibers and lamellae within the same colony, as shown in
 357 Figure S4.

358 Figure 4 b) shows the *lamellar* Mn profiles as solid and the *fibrous* as dash-dotted lines. Comparing the
 359 simulated Mn profiles after 50 s and 300 s, the fibrous profiles remain markedly less homogenized. This
 360 trend is consistent with the experimentally determined increase of the morphology ratio f_f/f_l over time.
 361 With increasing dwell time, the domains that retain their morphology longest are, therefore, not only
 362 coarser, but also increasingly fibrous. Other assumptions for the simulation of fibrous colonies are
 363 plausible as well, e.g. the fiber and lamella thickness may be kept identical while f_θ is adjusted
 364 accordingly. The corresponding simulated Mn profiles are shown in Figure S6. In that case, a much
 365 faster homogenization of the fibrous profile is observed, which is mainly attributed to the low initial f_θ .
 366 This, however, is not consistent with the experiments. The increasing f_f/f_l with increasing dwell time
 367 indicates that the first assumption captures the actual microstructure more realistically.

Figure 4: DICTRA simulations on the dissolution of 1D Mn concentration profiles at 770 °C. a) shows different lamellar spacings $s_{1,\theta}$ and b) the influence of fiber morphology on the Mn homogenization kinetics, while keeping all other input parameters constant.

368 Both simulations shown in Figure 4 a) and b) suggest that inhomogeneity of the initial pearlite is the
 369 root cause of the microstructure evolution discussed in (ii). While this assessment explains the
 370 morphological evolution, the changing f_γ are not immediately rationalized. In the present Fe-4.9Mn-
 371 2.7C alloy, the highest retained f_γ of (0.27 ± 0.03) is achieved in the STA150 and STA400 conditions,
 372 although their respective f_{hom} differ strongly, with (0.10 ± 0.05) vs (0.82 ± 0.06) . Even the fully
 373 homogenized STA5000 condition retains (0.24 ± 0.03) γ . The difference between the two alloys can be
 374 rationalized by local variations in f_γ between ghost pearlite domains, f_γ^{gp} , and homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$

375 domains, f_{γ}^{hom} . However, due to the microstructural mockup and length scales, the volume fraction data
376 of the individual domains is experimentally not immediately accessible. Therefore, Thermo-Calc
377 calculations on retained f_{γ} were employed. Calculated quantities will henceforth be indicated by '.

378 The retained f_{γ}' was calculated using the Property Model Calculator in Thermo-Calc. The model
379 requires composition, quenching temperature and γ grain size as input. The software is based on a semi-
380 empirical approach by Huyan et al. [44], which combines thermodynamic quantities, e.g. Gibbs free
381 energies of α'/γ , with fitted experimental parameters. In the framework of the Thermo-Calc software
382 another aspect must be considered. For compositions that exhibit both lath and plate α' , the one with
383 higher martensite start temperature M_s' will be considered. Consequently, unsuitable empirical fit
384 parameters and M_s' can both cause inaccurate results. To account for such inaccuracies, Thermo-Calc
385 allows for a Gibbs free energy manipulation of the initial γ . This parameter was calibrated using the
386 experimental chemical composition as well as f_{γ} of STA5000 and a γ grain size of 50 μm . All further
387 calculations were performed with a target temperature, Gibbs free energy change and grain size of 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$,
388 -200 J mol^{-1} and 50 μm , respectively.

389 Quantitatively meaningful calculations of retained f_{γ}' require an accurate description of the local
390 chemical composition during STA. In the present work, this composition was not treated as a single
391 value for each condition. Instead, f_{γ}' was calculated along the simulated concentration profiles obtained
392 from DICTRA simulations. The initial condition was based on average experimental data of *lamellar*
393 pearlite, with $s_1 = 180 \text{ nm}$, $x_{\text{Mn}}^{\theta} = 26.0 \text{ at. \%}$, $x_{\text{Mn}}^{\alpha} = 2.0 \text{ at. \%}$ and $f_{\theta} = 0.12$. C distribution was
394 assumed initially homogeneous with $\bar{x}_{\text{C}} = 2.7 \text{ at. \%}$. The simulated local compositions were first
395 validated by comparison with the corresponding 1D APT data for STA150 and STA400. As shown in
396 Figure 5 a) and c), the simulation slightly underestimates the degree of Mn homogenization for STA150,
397 whereas excellent agreement is obtained for STA400. Similarly, the C profiles are compared in
398 Figure S7. The predicted C accumulation in Mn rich regions is well represented in the experimental
399 data. Deviations in both conditions are likely due to the unknown initial state of the specific pearlite
400 colony analyzed by APT, while the simulations are based on average microstructural parameters. The
401 effect is expected to be strongest at early stages of homogenization, when the Mn profile is still sharp.

402 The validated composition profiles were then used as input for batch calculations of f_{γ}' after quenching
403 to RT. In this way, each local composition along the profile was converted into a corresponding local
404 value of retained f_{γ}' . The resulting f_{γ}' profiles for STA150 and STA400 are shown in Figure 5 b) and d),
405 respectively. Both contain entirely retained γ regions with widths of about 43 nm for STA150 and 39 nm
406 for STA400, highlighted by black arrows. These regions may correspond to γ lamellae of ghost pearlite.
407 With increasing dwell time, however, the concentration profiles broaden and retained f_{γ}' is no longer
408 restricted to these regions. The f_{γ}^{gp} of a ghost pearlite simulation cell was therefore obtained by
409 averaging the local f_{γ}' across the distance of $s_1/2$, which yields 0.29 for STA150 and 0.41 for STA400.
410 This result suggests that in the present alloy f_{γ}^{gp} may initially increase during STA before decreasing
411 again when chemical homogeneity is approached. An additional implication is that the ghost pearlite
412 may contain lamellae with mixed $\gamma + \alpha'$ rather than strictly alternating single-phase γ and α' lamellae.

413 To further assess the quantitative robustness of these calculations, the f_{γ}^{gp} results were correlated with
414 the experimental f_{γ} of STA150 and STA400. As both STA conditions are not exclusively comprised of
415 ghost pearlite, but also of homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$, a semi-empirical rule of mixture approach was applied
416 to calculate their global f_{γ}' . The following was assumed: (1) the simulated f_{γ}^{gp} represents the entirety

417 of ghost pearlite domains, while (2) the entirety of homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ domains is represented by the
 418 experimental results of STA5000 $f_{\gamma}^{\text{hom}} = 0.23$. As homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ regions in STA400 and
 419 STA5000 were shown to have comparable composition, they are expected to contribute the same amount
 420 of f_{γ} , irrespective of dwell time. Using

$$f_{\gamma}' = f_{\gamma}'^{\text{gp}} f_{\text{gp}} + f_{\gamma}'^{\text{hom}} f_{\text{hom}} \quad 6$$

421 yields a f_{γ}' of 0.29 for STA150 and 0.27 for STA400. These results agree well with the experimental f_{γ}
 422 of (0.27 ± 0.03) for both conditions.

423 The importance of considering f_{γ} on a domain-wise basis is highlighted by comparison with the work
 424 of Nuam et al. [13]. In their Fe-3.8Mn-1.3C-0.8Ni-1.2Si alloy, a comparable morphology evolution was
 425 observed, but f_{γ} decreased continuously with increasing f_{hom} [13]. The condition with the highest f_{γ} of
 426 (0.13 ± 0.01) still contained f_{hom} of (0.49 ± 0.05) , whereas the fully homogenized condition retained
 427 only (0.05 ± 0.01) [13]. Considering $f_{\gamma}'^{\text{hom}}$ to be (0.05 ± 0.01) , it becomes apparent that the increase in
 428 f_{hom} with increasing STA dwell time has stronger impact on f_{γ} in Ref. [13], than in the present alloy.
 429 The approach given in Eq. 5 therefore provides a useful framework for predicting the evolution of f_{γ} in
 430 chemically patterned $\gamma + \alpha'$ microstructures, given that the domain fractions and their characteristic
 431 retained γ contributions are known.

Figure 5: DICTRA simulations (dot-dashed lines) and experimental 1D Mn concentration profiles (solid lines) for a) STA150 in blue and c) STA400 in orange. b) and d) show the retained γ fraction f_{γ}' of the simulated concentration profiles (dotted lines) calculated at RT for STA150 and STA400, respectively. The simulation time is reduced by 100 s compared to the experiment, to account for the γ transformation interval.

4. Mechanical Properties

4.1. Experimental Results

432 Vickers hardness measurements H were carried out for the pearlitic condition and the different STA
 433 states with the results being summarized in Table 3. The pearlitic microstructure showed a H of
 434 (244 ± 8) HV1. After STA treatment and quenching, H increased to (742 ± 19) HV1 for STA150,
 435 (731 ± 12) HV1 for STA400, and (690 ± 11) HV1 for STA5000. Thus, all STA conditions exhibited
 436 substantially higher H than the initial pearlite, while a moderate decrease was observed with increasing
 437 STA duration, and thus, increasing f_{hom} . Literature data of a Fe-5.0Mn-1.8C medium Mn steel with
 438 comparable microstructural mockup to STA400 and a f_{γ} of approximately 0.20, shows a H of
 439 (660 ± 10) HV10. The slightly lower H can be attributed to both the higher load during testing [45] and
 440 a lower overall C content of 1.8 at.% compared to the 2.7 at.% in the present alloy [46].

Table 3: Summary of the mechanical properties of the investigated conditions. Hardness was determined in HV1. The offset yield strengths were obtained for 1 % (σ_{p1}) and 5 % (σ_{p5}) of plastic strain via compression tests performed at an initial strain rate of $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

	Hardness		Offset yield strength	
	H		σ_{p1}	σ_{p5}
	HV1		MPa	
Pearlite	244 ± 8		572 ± 16	860 ± 11
STA150	742 ± 19		2079 ± 174	2654 ± 205
STA400	731 ± 12		2086 ± 82	2809 ± 101
STA5000	690 ± 11		1890 ± 12	2587 ± 26

441 To investigate the work hardening behavior and the γ stability during deformation, RT compression tests
 442 were performed. Representative true stress–true strain curves of deliberately interrupted tests are shown
 443 in Figure 6 a), together with the corresponding Kocks-Mecking plots in Figure 6 b). The true offset yield
 444 strengths were determined at 1 % (σ_{p1}) and 5 % (σ_{p5}) plastic strain, to characterize both the onset of
 445 plastic flow and the subsequent increase in flow stress during continued deformation. These results are
 446 summarized in Table 3. The σ_{p1} and σ_{p5} determined for pearlite with a s_1 of (180 ± 18) nm agree well
 447 with literature data on flow stresses of similarly spaced aggregates [47]. After STA, a pronounced
 448 increase in strength was observed compared to the initial pearlite, as was already shown in the original
 449 work of Sun et al. [11]. The initial pearlite exhibits a σ_{p1} of (572 ± 16) MPa, whereas substantially
 450 higher values were recorded for all STA conditions, namely (2079 ± 174) MPa for STA150,
 451 (2086 ± 82) MPa for STA400 and (1890 ± 12) MPa for STA5000. This trend is consistent with the
 452 hardness data. In particular, STA150 and STA400 exhibit nearly identical σ_{p1} and H , despite the
 453 pronounced microstructural change from almost no homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ in STA150 with a fraction of
 454 (0.10 ± 0.06) to a predominant occurrence of these domains in STA400 with (0.82 ± 0.05) . By contrast,
 455 STA5000 shows a moderate reduction in both hardness and σ_{p1} , consistent with complete Mn
 456 homogenization and the associated loss of the chemically patterned microstructure [13]. Evaluating the
 457 σ_{p5} data, STA400 shows the highest strength at (2809 ± 101) MPa, despite having nearly the same σ_{p1}
 458 as STA150 with (2086 ± 82) MPa vs. (2079 ± 174) MPa, indicating a greater capacity for work
 459 hardening during compression. STA150 reaches a slightly lower σ_{p5} of (2654 ± 205) MPa, whereas

460 STA5000 exhibits the lowest among the STA conditions at (2587 ± 26) MPa. Thus, STA5000 remains
 461 below STA150 and STA400 in both σ_{p1} and σ_{p5} , consistent with comparable microstructures in a
 462 hypoeutectoid Fe-3.76Mn-1.33C-0.76Ni-1.17Si alloy [13]. This interpretation on work hardening
 463 behavior is supported by the Kocks-Mecking plots in Figure 6 b), which show superior work hardening
 464 of STA400 (orange line) compared to STA150 (blue line) and STA5000 (black line) at every true stress
 465 level. Generally, all conditions show a decline in work hardening with increasing flow stress.

Figure 6: Representative true compressive stress-strain curves as well as Kocks-Mecking plots of all conditions in a) and b), respectively. Tests were performed at an initial strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} and deliberately interrupted, indicated via arrows in a).

466 Ex-situ neutron diffraction experiments were performed on STA samples of all conditions before and
 467 after deformation to $\sim 11\%$ true total strain ($\sim 9\%$ plastic strain) to determine lattice constants and
 468 volume specific phase fractions. While the lattice constants of γ in any of the conditions are not expected
 469 to change significantly, DIMT of γ , stress partitioning between γ and α' as well as C segregation on
 470 newly formed defects may impact the lattice constants of α' . An example of a refinement for the STA150
 471 is shown in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** a) for an undeformed and in b) for
 472 a deformed sample. No peaks associated with hexagonal ϵ martensite were found. The derived data is
 473 summarized in Table 4. Comparing the lattice constants of γ before and after deformation, expectedly
 474 no significant changes were observed for STA150 and STA400. STA5000 on the other hand showed a
 475 slight increase of a_γ from $(3.592 \pm 0.001) \text{ \AA}$ to $(3.598 \pm 0.003) \text{ \AA}$. This difference is most likely caused
 476 by fitting inaccuracies due to peak broadening and small f_γ in the deformed sample. In terms of the α'
 477 tetragonality, all conditions show a reduction in their respective $c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$ ratios from (1.023 ± 0.002) to
 478 (1.014 ± 0.005) , without a clear correlation to underlying ghost pearlite fraction. Such a reduction is
 479 likely caused by newly formed defects and C segregation to them, comparable to what is shown in the
 480 as-quenched condition in Figure 2 e). α' formed via DIMT may also affect $c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$, due to local
 481 chemistry of the retained γ . As these domains are either comparable in composition to pre-existing α' in
 482 case of homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ domains or enriched in C and Mn in the ghost pearlite domains, it is unlikely
 483 to contribute to the reduction of $c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$.

484 Prior to deformation, all conditions contained comparable amounts of retained γ , with volume fractions
 485 of (0.27 ± 0.03) for STA150 as well as STA400 and (0.24 ± 0.03) for STA5000. After deformation, the
 486 γ fraction decreased markedly to (0.08 ± 0.03) , (0.07 ± 0.03) , and (0.07 ± 0.03) , respectively,
 487 demonstrating that most of the γ transformed into α' during compression. This pronounced reduction in
 488 γ fraction reveals substantial DIMT in all STA conditions. The deformed microstructures of STA150
 489 and STA400 indicate negligible inhomogeneous deformation between the ghost pearlite and

490 homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ domains. Micrographs of an undeformed and a deformed sample of the STA400
 491 condition are shown in Figure S8 a) and b), respectively.

Table 4: Summary of lattice parameters a_i , $c_{\alpha'}$, the ratio $c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$ and phase fractions f_i for a phase i before and after deformation for the STA conditions. All parameters were determined via ex-situ neutron diffraction experiments.

	Strain ϵ_{total} %	Phase i	Lattice constants			Volume fraction f_i
			a_i	$c_{\alpha'}$ Å	$c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$	
STA150	0	γ	3.593 ± 0.004	–	–	0.27 ± 0.03
		α'	2.861 ± 0.002	2.923 ± 0.003	1.022 ± 0.001	0.73 ± 0.03
	11.2	γ	3.593 ± 0.006	–	–	0.08 ± 0.03
		α'	2.866 ± 0.003	2.904 ± 0.010	1.013 ± 0.004	0.92 ± 0.03
STA400	0	γ	3.592 ± 0.002	–	–	0.27 ± 0.03
		α'	2.862 ± 0.001	2.930 ± 0.002	1.024 ± 0.001	0.73 ± 0.03
	11.5	γ	3.594 ± 0.004	–	–	0.07 ± 0.03
		α'	2.863 ± 0.002	2.905 ± 0.001	1.015 ± 0.003	0.93 ± 0.03
STA5000	0	γ	3.592 ± 0.001	–	–	0.24 ± 0.03
		α'	2.862 ± 0.001	2.929 ± 0.002	1.023 ± 0.000	0.76 ± 0.03
	11.5	γ	3.598 ± 0.003	–	–	0.07 ± 0.03
		α'	2.866 ± 0.004	2.910 ± 0.004	1.015 ± 0.001	0.93 ± 0.03

Figure 7: Diffraction pattern and respective fits for samples in STA150 condition: a) undeformed state, and b) deformed condition with a true total strain of 11.2%. α' and γ fits as well as peak positions are indicated in blue and red, respectively. Potential peak positions of hexagonal ϵ martensite are shown in gold, using lattice parameters provided in Ref. [48].

4.2. Discussion

492 The σ_{p1} of STA150 and STA400 are nearly identical with (2079 ± 174) MPa and (2086 ± 82) MPa,
 493 while STA5000 shows a slight reduction with (1890 ± 12) MPa. The same trend is observed in H .
 494 Therefore, both can be used as descriptors for the present yielding behaviors. For further discussion,
 495 yield strength will be considered and referred to as σ_{p1} . As all conditions share the same overall
 496 composition, the main contributions to σ_{p1} are the refined morphology of ghost pearlite, overall phase
 497 fractions of soft γ and hard α' , as well as the local composition of α' . At small strains, DIMT is not
 498 expected to contribute substantially, so the comparable yielding behavior must mainly reflect the
 499 resistance of the existing $\gamma + \alpha'$ microstructures to the onset of plastic flow [49, 50]. A lamellar/fibrous
 500 microstructure contributes to σ_{p1} via small lamellar/fiber spacing [51, 52]. In ideal, transformation-free
 501 laminates comprising a soft and a hard phase, deformation with increasing strain may be described in
 502 three stages [53]: (i) elastic deformation of both phases, (ii) yielding and plastic flow of the softer phase
 503 via the activation of slip systems with low critical shear stress and (iii) plastic flow of both phases due
 504 to back stress evolution induced by the inhomogeneous plastic deformation. In the present case where
 505 σ_{p1} is at 1 % plastic strain, both phases are expected to have plastically deformed. The diminishing of
 506 fine-structured ghost pearlite with increasing dwell time is therefore expected to lead to a decrease in
 507 σ_{p1} . Superimposed to this are two aspects that lead to an increase in σ_{p1} when the microstructure reaches
 508 chemical homogeneity: Both (a) the overall fraction of the harder α' , and (b) the average Mn and C
 509 content in α' increase. The effect of (a) is limited, as there is only a marginal increase from (0.73 ± 0.03)
 510 to (0.76 ± 0.03) . However, (b) is expected to enhance σ_{p1} of chemically heterogeneous conditions like

511 STA5000 significantly [46, 54]. As the change in these contributions occurs simultaneously and
512 codependently, more quantitative discussions are obstructed.

513 All STA conditions exhibit high work hardening, exceeding 20 GPa at a true stress of 2000 MPa,
514 followed by a continuous decrease with increasing flow stress. This generally high work hardening can
515 be attributed to two contributions. First, all conditions show substantial DIMT, i.e. transformation from
516 soft γ to hard α' . Second, the α' matrix itself contributes through plastic deformation, as indicated by the
517 marked reduction in tetragonality after compression. These two contributions, however, do not
518 immediately explain why STA400 exhibits the highest work hardening capability, i.e. ~ 5 GPa at
519 3000 MPa true stress. The decisive difference lies in the distribution of γ between the different
520 microstructural domains. Although STA150 and STA400 both contain approximately the same global
521 retained f_γ of (0.27 ± 0.03) , their local f_γ may be very different. The DICTRA-based calculations
522 presented in Chapter 3.2 suggest that the retained γ fraction inside ghost pearlite domains, f_γ^{GP} , may
523 increase from 0.29 in STA150 to 0.41 in STA400. Taking the homogeneous domains as $f_\gamma^{\text{hom}} = 0.23$,
524 the domain-to-domain difference in retained γ rises from 0.06 for STA150 to 0.18 for STA400.
525 Additionally, the γ in the ghost pearlite domains of STA400 is expected to be less stable than in STA150
526 because local homogenization has already progressed further [10]. STA400 therefore combines a higher
527 local γ fraction with a lower local γ stability in the ghost pearlite domains. This should broaden the
528 distribution of local transformation conditions and promote a more progressive DIMT compared to both
529 STA150 and STA5000.

530 The importance of a controlled γ stability distribution for work hardening was already proposed by
531 Sun et al. [11]. In their work on a Fe-4.3Mn-2.3C alloy, STA was carried out at 770 °C with a dwell
532 time aimed at obtaining a high, although not quantified, fraction of ghost pearlite in the as-quenched
533 condition. To achieve meaningful plastic deformation under tensile loading, additional tempering
534 treatments were employed, e.g. for 30 s at 400 °C and 300 °C. After yielding, both conditions showed a
535 decreasing work hardening rate, with the decrease being more gradual after tempering at 300 °C. In this
536 condition, the work hardening rate declined continuously to ~ 13 GPa at 2000 MPa true stress. After
537 tempering at 400 °C, the same work hardening rate was already reached at ~ 1600 MPa and at lower
538 total engineering strain, i.e. ~ 2 % vs. ~ 5 %. Sun et al. [11] attributed the superior work hardening of
539 the 300 °C condition to its higher initial f_γ of (0.23 ± 0.02) and to the more progressive transformation
540 with increasing deformation.

541 A recent study by Luo et al. [49] provides direct quantitative support for the idea that progressive work
542 hardening is governed not simply by f_γ , but by the distribution of γ metastability within the
543 microstructure. Using Fe-5.1Mn-0.5C model alloys, intercritically annealed at 640 °C, the authors
544 produced four microstructures with comparable γ chemistry but systematic variations in γ
545 morphology [49]. Three globular microstructures with different mean γ diameters, and one lath-shaped
546 microstructure were designed. Initial f_γ were comparable (~ 0.23 – 0.27) across all conditions [49]. In-
547 situ neutron diffraction showed that the DIMT was strain-driven and that its average rate scaled inversely
548 with γ metastability. The coarsest globular condition transformed fastest, at about 0.04 per 1 % plastic
549 strain, whereas the lath-shaped condition transformed slowest, at about 0.02 per 1 % plastic strain. This
550 difference was reflected directly in the macroscopic response. The lath-shaped microstructure exhibited
551 a superior combination of ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and uniform elongation (UE), with 1139 MPa
552 and 32.1 %, respectively. By contrast, the globular condition reached a similar UTS of 1113 MPa but
553 only 14.3 % UE. The origin of this difference does not lie exclusively within the difference in
554 morphology, but rather the distribution of effective γ sizes which is wider for the lath-shaped

555 microstructure [49]. In the present microstructures, such a wide range of γ stability can be designed
556 through local variations in chemical composition and through the coexistence of domains with different
557 γ morphology.

558 A further potential contribution to work hardening in the present microstructures stems from the
559 evolution of stress partitioning between γ and α' during deformation. Mao et al. [50] quantified this
560 effect in a Fe-22.9Ni-1.4C steel using in-situ synchrotron XRD experiments. They showed that the stress
561 partitioning rate can contribute to the global work hardening rate on a similar scale than the γ to α'
562 transformation rate itself. This contribution originates predominantly from elastic loading of newly
563 formed α' by the plastic flow of the surrounding γ matrix. The α' phase stress increases from ~ 750 MPa
564 to ~ 2000 MPa between 23 % and 36 % total true strain and saturates once α' begins to deform
565 plastically. Since $\sigma_{p1} > 1800$ MPa in the present STA conditions, only limited additional stress
566 partitioning can develop during deformation. Its contribution to work hardening is therefore expected to
567 be limited.

5. Conclusions

568 A near eutectoid Fe-4.9Mn-2.7C alloy was subjected to a pearlite treatment fulfilling the Mn partitioning
569 criterion only for α/γ , but not for θ/γ and therefore outside conventional partitioning regimes. Despite
570 this, a complete transformation with significant Mn partitioning into θ of (23.6–28.8) at.% was achieved,
571 consistent with earlier assessments [25]. After the pearlite formation, several STA treatments at 770 °C
572 for a dwell time of 150 s, 400 s and 5000 s were applied. The aim was to manipulate the Mn
573 concentration profile and thus key properties like phase fractions and γ stability. With respect to the
574 initial objectives, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 575 • Ghost pearlite forms as a transient microstructure during STA of Mn-partitioned pearlite and
576 disappears progressively as Mn homogenization proceeds. Its stability is controlled by initial
577 pearlite heterogeneity, especially θ morphology and lamellar/fiber spacing. As a result,
578 intermediate microstructures between pearlite, ghost pearlite and homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ will form.
- 579 • The microstructure evolution during STA presented here and in Refs. [13, 21] occurs
580 irrespective of alloy composition as long as Mn partitioning pearlite is established initially and
581 the Mn and C lean γ domains can transform to α' . However, significant differences are expected
582 in the evolution of retained γ . Steels with low concentrations of γ stabilizers will yield high γ
583 fractions in ghost pearlite, while homogenous domains are thermodynamically limited in their
584 contribution. This leads to a continuous decrease of f_γ with increasing STA dwell time.
585 Increasing the amount of γ stabilizers, e.g. Mn and C, leads to a significantly higher f_γ in regions
586 of chemically homogenous $\gamma + \alpha'$, which may even reach 1. Then, martensitic transformation
587 would only be possible in Mn and C lean regions of chemically inhomogeneous γ .
- 588 • Microstructure evolution during STA, as well as the retained γ fractions after quenching, can be
589 predicted by simple CALPHAD-based calculations when the essential parameters of the initial
590 pearlite and volume fractions of relevant domains in the STA conditions are known. This shows
591 that the complexity of the transient microstructures can be reduced to a small number of
592 physically meaningful parameters, i.e. x_{Mn}^θ , f_θ , s_l and f_{hom} .
- 593 • The highest work hardening capability was obtained for the STA400 condition comprised of
594 both ghost pearlite and homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ domains. This indicates that the most favorable
595 microstructure is not an entirely retained ultrafine ghost pearlite, but a morphologically and
596 chemically heterogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ condition with a wide range of γ stabilities. A controlled

597 intermediate degree of Mn homogenization therefore appears more beneficial for sustaining
598 continuous high work hardening than either complete morphological inheritance or complete
599 homogenization.

6. Acknowledgements

600 This work has been supported via personal grants by the Landesgraduiertenförderung (LGF) by the local
601 state of Baden-Württemberg (Germany) and the GRAFÖG funding by the German Academic Exchange
602 Service (DAAD). This work was partly carried out with the support of the Karlsruhe Nano Micro
603 Facility (KNMFi, www.knmf.kit.edu), an Open Access Research Infrastructure within the Karlsruhe
604 High Technology Hub at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT – The University in the Helmholtz
605 Association, www.kit.edu). The synchrotron XRD experiments (proposal no. 2024B1779) at SPring-8
606 (Super Photon ring-8 GeV) were conducted with the approval of the Japan Synchrotron Radiation
607 Research Institute (JASRI).

Conflict of Interest

608 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

609 The data presented in this study are available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20424699>
610 under CC BY-SA 4.0 license. Further information is available upon request with [marcel.muench-](mailto:marcel.muench-14k@rub.de)
611 14k@rub.de.

7. Author Contributions

Marcel Muench: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Funding acquisition, Writing - original draft.

Jan Lars Riedel: Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing - Review & Editing.

Sandipan Sen: Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing - Review & Editing.

Si Gao: Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing.

Wu Gong: Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing.

Yolita M. Eggeler: Methodology, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing.

Nobuhiro Tsuji: Methodology, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing.

Martin Heilmaier: Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Writing - Review & Editing.

Alexander Kauffmann: Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Visualization, Funding acquisition, Writing - Review & Editing.

8. Options for Contributions

Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition

9. References

- [1] Raabe, D. et al.: Current Challenges and Opportunities in Microstructure-Related Properties of Advanced High-Strength Steels. *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, **51** (11), 2020, p. 5517–5586.
- [2] Tasan, C.C. et al.: An Overview of Dual-Phase Steels: Advances in Microstructure-Oriented Processing and Micromechanically Guided Design. *Annual Review of Materials Research*, **45**, 2015, p. 391–431.
- [3] Lavakumar, A. et al.: Role of surrounding phases on deformation-induced martensitic transformation of retained austenite in multi-phase TRIP steel. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **874**, 2023, p. 145089.
- [4] Pierce, D.T. et al.: The influence of stacking fault energy on the microstructural and strain-hardening evolution of Fe–Mn–Al–Si steels during tensile deformation. *Acta Materialia*, **100**, 2015, p. 178–190.
- [5] Grässel, O. et al.: High strength Fe–Mn–(Al, Si) TRIP/TWIP steels development — properties — application. *International Journal of Plasticity*, **16** (10), 2000, p. 1391–1409.
- [6] Edmonds, D.V. et al.: Quenching and partitioning martensite—A novel steel heat treatment. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **438–440**, 2006, p. 25–34.
- [7] Speer, J.G. et al.: Critical Assessment 7: Quenching and partitioning. *Materials Science and Technology*, **31** (1), 2015, p. 3–9.
- [8] Li, Y. et al.: A review of the thermal stability of metastable austenite in steels: Martensite formation. *Journal of Materials Science & Technology*, **91**, 2021, p. 200–214.
- [9] Miller, R.L.: Ultrafine-grained microstructures and mechanical properties of alloy steels. *Metallurgical Transactions*, **3** (4), 1972, p. 905–912.
- [10] Sun, B. et al.: Physical metallurgy of medium-Mn advanced high-strength steels. *International Materials Reviews*, **68** (7), 2023, p. 786–824.
- [11] Sun, W.W. et al.: Advanced high strength steel (AHSS) development through chemical patterning of austenite. *Scripta Materialia*, **146** (5), 2018, p. 60–63.
- [12] Wang, M.-M. et al.: Nanolaminate transformation-induced plasticity–twinning-induced plasticity steel with dynamic strain partitioning and enhanced damage resistance. *Acta Materialia*, **85**, 2015, p. 216–228.
- [13] Nuam, V.L. et al.: Microstructure evolution and synergistic improvement of strength-ductility through partitioned pearlite-based quenching and tempering process. *Materials Characterization*, **231**, 2026, p. 115922.
- [14] Yang, D. et al.: Quenching and partitioning in Si/Al-free steels: effect of Mn-heterogeneous distribution in high-temperature austenite. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **941**, 2025, p. 148622.
- [15] Yang, D. et al.: Mn Heterogeneity and Ductility Improvement Realized by Slow Heating Mn-Partitioned Pearlite. *Metals and Materials International*, **30** (2), 2024, p. 393–402.

- [16] Zhang, C. et al.: Heterogeneous quenching and partitioning from manganese-partitioned pearlite: retained austenite modification and formability improvement. *Acta Materialia*, **235**, 2022, p. 118060.
- [17] Ren, W. et al.: The Effect of Heating Rate on the Microstructure Evolution and Hardness of Heterogeneous Manganese Steel. *Materials*, **17** (21), 2024, p. 5321.
- [18] Yang, D. et al.: Effect of partitioning time on the microstructure and properties of chemical heterogeneous quenched and partitioned steels. *Materials Characterization*, **227**, 2025, p. 115282.
- [19] Zhang, C. et al.: Chemical patterning enhanced by increasing quenching temperature in a medium-Mn steel. *Journal of Iron and Steel Research International*, **30** (10), 2023, p. 1916–1920.
- [20] Liu, G. et al.: Kinetic transitions and Mn partitioning during austenite growth from a mixture of partitioned cementite and ferrite: Role of heating rate. *Journal of Materials Science & Technology*, **49**, 2020, p. 70–80.
- [21] Yang, D. et al.: Lamellar Pearlite as an Initial Microstructure for Austenite Reversion Treatment. *Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance*, **30** (2), 2021, p. 1330–1339.
- [22] Hutchinson, C.R. et al.: The growth of partitioned pearlite in Fe–C–Mn steels. *Acta Materialia*, **52** (12), 2004, p. 3565–3585.
- [23] Coates, D.E.: Diffusional growth limitation and hardenability. *Metallurgical Transactions*, **4** (10), 1973, p. 2313–2325.
- [24] Philibert, J. et al.: *Thermodynamics and Phase Transformations: The selected works of Mats Hillert*. Les Ulis: EDP Sciences, 2021.
- [25] Muench, M. et al.: Compositional requirements for the synthesis of Fe–Mn–C austenite-martensite composites: Beyond local equilibrium considerations in pearlite formation. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, **39**, 2025, p. 8984–8993.
- [26] Schneider, C.A. et al.: NIH Image to ImageJ: 25 years of image analysis. *Nature Methods*, **9** (7), 2012, p. 671–675.
- [27] Gault, B. et al.: Atom probe tomography. *Nature Reviews Methods Primers*, **1** (1), 2021, p. 1–30.
- [28] Schwarz, T.M. et al.: In Situ Metallic Coating of Atom Probe Specimen for Enhanced Yield, Performance, and Increased Field-of-View. *Microscopy and Microanalysis*, **30** (6), 2024, p. 1109–1123.
- [29] Harjo, S. et al.: Current Status of Engineering Materials Diffractometer at J-PARC. *Materials Science Forum*, **681**, 2011, p. 443–448.
- [30] Toby, B.H., Von Dreele, R.B.: GSAS-II: the genesis of a modern open-source all purpose crystallography software package. *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, **46** (2), 2013, p. 544–549.
- [31] Mehl, R.F., Hagel, W.C.: The austenite: Pearlite reaction. *Progress in Metal Physics*, **6**, 1956, p. 74–134.
- [32] Zhang, M.-X., Kelly, P.M.: The morphology and formation mechanism of pearlite in steels. *Materials Characterization*, **60** (6), 2009, p. 545–554.
- [33] Kitahara, H. et al.: Crystallographic features of lath martensite in low-carbon steel. *Acta Materialia*, **54** (5), 2006, p. 1279–1288.

- [34] Stormvinter, A. et al.: Effect of carbon content on variant pairing of martensite in Fe–C alloys. *Acta Materialia*, **60** (20), 2012, p. 7265–7274.
- [35] Song, W. et al.: Carbon Redistribution in Martensite in High-C Steel: Atomic-Scale Characterization and Modelling. *Metals*, **8** (8), 2018.
- [36] Dyson, D.J., Holmes, B.: Effect of Alloying Additions on the Lattice Parameter of Austenite. *Journal of the Iron and Steel Institute*, **208** (5), 1970, p. 469–474.
- [37] Lu, Y. et al.: The effect of carbon content on the c/a ratio of as-quenched martensite in Fe-C alloys. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **700**, 2017, p. 592–597.
- [38] Crank, J.: *The Mathematics of Diffusion*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1975.
- [39] Li, S. et al.: Study of partition to non-partition transition of austenite growth along pearlite lamellae in near-eutectoid Fe-C-Mn alloy. *Acta Materialia*, **177**, 2019, p. 198–208.
- [40] Hillert, M. et al.: Effect of alloying elements on the formation of austenite and dissolution of cementite. *Journal of the Iron and Steel Institute*, **209** (1), 1971, p. 49–66.
- [41] Shtansky, D.V. et al.: Pearlite to austenite transformation in an Fe–2.6Cr–1C alloy. *Acta Materialia*, **47** (9), 1999, p. 2619–2632.
- [42] Xia, Y. et al.: Effects of alloying elements on the kinetics of austenitization from pearlite in Fe–C–M alloys. *Philosophical Magazine*, **93** (9), 2013, p. 1095–1109.
- [43] Miyamoto, G. et al.: Effects of Mn, Si and Cr addition on reverse transformation at 1073 K from spheroidized cementite structure in Fe–0.6 mass% C alloy. *Acta Materialia*, **58** (13), 2010, p. 4492–4502.
- [44] Huyan, F. et al.: A Thermodynamic-Based Model to Predict the Fraction of Martensite in Steels. *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, **47** (9), 2016, p. 4404–4410.
- [45] Nix, W.D., Gao, H.: Indentation size effects in crystalline materials: A law for strain gradient plasticity. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **46** (3), 1998, p. 411–425.
- [46] Hutchinson, B. et al.: Microstructures and hardness of as-quenched martensites (0.1–0.5%C). *Acta Materialia*, **59** (14), 2011, p. 5845–5858.
- [47] Dollar, M. et al.: Influence of deformation substructure on flow and fracture of fully pearlitic steel. *Acta Metallurgica*, **36** (2), 1988, p. 311–320.
- [48] Marinelli, P. et al.: Lattice Parameters of Metastable Structures in Quenched Fe-Mn Alloys. Part II: hcp Phase. *International Journal of Materials Research*, **92** (5), 2001, p. 489–493.
- [49] Luo, J. et al.: Deconvoluting the effects of austenite grain size and shape on the strain-induced martensitic transformation in medium-Mn steels. *Acta Materialia*, **296**, 2025, p. 121298.
- [50] Mao, W. et al.: Quantitatively evaluating respective contribution of austenite and deformation-induced martensite to flow stress, plastic strain, and strain hardening rate in tensile deformed TRIP steel. *Acta Materialia*, **256**, 2023, p. 119139.
- [51] Maruyama, K. et al.: Effects of lamellar spacing on mechanical properties of fully lamellar Ti–39.4mol%Al alloy. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **319–321**, 2001, p. 360–363.
- [52] Mishra, K., Singh, A.: Effect of interlamellar spacing on fracture toughness of nano-structured pearlite. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **706**, 2017, p. 22–26.

- [53] Klein, C., Böhlke, T.: Gradient Crystal Plasticity Modeling of Laminate Microstructures. *GAMM-Mitteilungen*, **48** (4), 2025, p. 1–24.
- [54] Arlazarov, A. et al.: Characterization and Modeling of Manganese Effect on Strength and Strain Hardening of Martensitic Carbon Steels. *ISIJ International*, **53** (6), 2013, p. 1076–1080.